

Levels of styrene oligomers measured in food simulants show that health risks are unlikely

BfR Opinion 023/2016 of 21 April 2016

Polystyrenes are plastics which are also used for food contact materials such as packagings and utensils. In addition to polystyrene, smaller molecules (styrene oligomers) which can transfer from the material to the food are also produced during the manufacturing process. A transfer (migration) of styrene oligomers of up to 51 micrograms per kilogram of food simulant ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) was measured by an official food control laboratory.

The Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) has evaluated whether migrations of this kind pose a health risk to consumers. Overall, it was shown on the basis of published toxicological data that no health effects are to be assumed with migrations of styrene oligomers to foods at the levels measured.

The full version of this BfR Information is available in German on <http://www.bfr.bund.de/cm/343/gemessene-gehalte-an-styrol-oligomeren-in-lebensmittelsimulanzien-gesundheitliche-risiken-sind-unwahrscheinlich.pdf>

About the BfR

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